

THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE AND PLACE OF FICTION IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada o'zbek xalq ertaklarining maktab adabiyoti darsliklarida o'qitilishi va uning tarbiyaviy ahamiyati haqida fikrlar bildirilgan bo'lib, o'zbek xalq ertaklarining janr xususiyatlari, poetikasi, ertakchilik an'analari va ertak ijrochiligi o'rganilish tarixi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: folklorshunoslik, adabiyot, ertak, matal, cho'pchak, tafakkur, metod, etuk.

Annatation: this article discusses the teaching of Uzbek folk tales in school textbooks and its educational significance, the genre features of Uzbek folk tales, poetics, of fairy tale traditions and the history of the study of fairy tales.

Keywords: folklorist literature, fairy tale, mature, proverb, chap, contemplation, method.

Аннаотация: в статью рассматривается преподавание узбекских народных сказок в школьных учебниках и его воспитательное значение жанровые особенности узбекских народных поэтикаб сказочных традиций и история изучения сказок .

Ключевый слова: фольклор, литература, сказка, колени, пословица.

From the first years of independence, the country has risen to the level of state policy to pay high attention and care for young people. Because young people are

the future of the country. In order to further deepen the state policy in this area, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Youth Policy,, was adopted in a new edition. All of this is bearing fruit today. Our youth is making progress in business, science, culture, art, literature and sports. All this testifies to the fact that a generation worthy of our great ancestors is growing up.

The school that lays the foundation for our education not only teaches students to read, but also educates them to be independent thinkers. In order to arouse students’ interest in books and works of art, the main criterion of today’s education system is to acquaint them with works of various genres so that they can become conscious readers. “ Education and enlightenment are the main factors of human well-being, they call people to goodness, generosity and patience” (page 15) said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasizing the importance of educating young people. In this sense, increasing the desire to learn more. Samples of folklore, a rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people, are a great source of spiritual and enlightenment for primary school readers. Folk tales are especially important here. It is necessary to improve the educational aspects of students with the help of these works. Literature classes should be considered as a full-fledged course, with conversations, quizzes, analysis, disclosure, discussion of the protagonists’ actions, and the inculcation of patriotic and hardworking ideas. We should be proud of the centuries-old national values of our people, their unique customs, rituals and traditions.

It is well known that values are formed under certain conditions. Therefore, they will exist in local, national, regional and universal form and content. Fairy tales are one of the most popular and widespread genres of Uzbek folklore, which reflect the centuries-old life experience, wisdom and dreams of our people. As in the folklore of other nations, in Uzbek folk tales, the nations of nature and society are presented in a variety of artistic images. Fairy tales are an epic genre of folklore, created by a hardworking masses and preserved by storytellers for many centuries, closely connected with folk traditions, expressing socio-political, economic life

through fantasy and artistic fiction. Initially, the term fairy tale appears in a mature form in Muhmud Kashgari's „Devonulogatut Turk ‘’ . The fairy tale is found in different parts of the country under different names in the vernacular. For example, in Surtkhandarya, Samarkand, Fergana among Uzbeks it is called matal, in districts and villages of Bukhara region it is called ushuk, in Khorezm it is called varsoqi, in Tashkent and its environs it is called chopchak. The fact that fairy-tale life is depicted on the basis of fantasy and life fiction, based on the means of magic and sorcery, the fact that events and actions take place in wonderful - strange movements, differs from other genres of folklore by the supernatural courage of the protagonists. Significant work has been done and is being done in the field of collection and publication of Uzbek folk tales. In this regard, we should acknowledge the efforts of the famous folklorist the Great Karimi. Unfortunately, the scientist did not complete this work. After that, the combines truth and falsehood’’. Uzbek folk tales have a wide range of topics, regardless of their type, they all glorify such beautiful qualities as goodness, kindness, friendship, patriotism and these qualities are unique. -- solemnly defeats the vices that oppose him. The reason why fairy tales quickly affect the minds of children is that their language is simple, close to the vernacular, interesting, incredible events, and the adventurous lifestyle of favorite characters. If you pay attention, if you tell children a poem, a story, a riddle or a proverb, they will not be interested and listen carefully, but if you tell or read a story, their whole body will listen to you. The actions of the protagonists make them happy, the students live with those protagonists in life and try to learn the skills and actions they need in them, and sometimes they enter the image of their favorite fairy-tale heroes.

The sharp plot of the fairy tale, the unexpected wonderful situations in the course of events fascinate children the strong, courageous, resourceful heroes in any difficulties attract children. In many Uzbek folk tales, such themes as diligence, kindness, hospitality, honesty, friendship are sung. Proper use of proverbs, various parables, and artistic means in them also adds to its interestingness. It is also useful to memorize the proverbs in fairy tales, to teach them to interpret the content of

artistic means, to ask the meaning of new words. The form of the story, which is typical of fairy tales, the repetition of the same words and phrases ensures the melody and impact of the fairy tale. The value of fairy tales in school literature textbooks is that students realized that through the victory of good over evil, honesty, the heroes of fairy tales are always free from difficulties, and tell each other that this will be the case in life. This, of course, has a positive effect on the upbringing of the younger generation. In the course of the lesson it is important to teach not only to read the story, but also to tell it, to interpret its content independently. Telling a fairy tale enhances oral discourse, enriching your students' vocabulary. We know that children are more interested in magic and fairy tales about animals. In the primary grades, fairy tales about animals are taught more and more. Positive morals such as honesty, loyalty, kindness are presented in the image of an ant, goat, donkey, dog, rooster. We all know the fairy tale "Susambil", as the most beautiful example of a fairy tale about animals. In this tale donkey, oxen, rooster and bees become one body, defeating wild animals and gaining Susambil. Pupils want strange events to happen in life, such as the fact that the heroes of fairy tales are always able to do magical things, to get rid of their enemies or the calamities that befell them in supernatural ways. Such fairy tales as "Ur to'qmoq", "Uchar gilam", "Malikayi Husnobod", from a strong imagination in children and expand their imagination. Discussing the behavior of the protagonists of the fairy tale, along with developing the ability to evaluate, inspires confidence that good will always prevail.

Today's student's worldview, thinking, attitude to reality is different from yesterday. In an age of advanced information technology and rapid information exchange, a student growing up in a virtual world will no doubt be bored with traditional lessons. The main goal of the devotees of education is to fight hard to prevent the emptiness in the minds of students at such time. Of course, literature lessons are invaluable in this situation. Today's demand is the introduction of interactive methods in the classroom, designed to bring literature lessons in terms of

form and content. Therefore, in the lessons of literature in secondary schools are able to make new discoveries in the teaching of didactic fairy tales, embodying the rich history, customs, unique traditions, noble goals of our people, creative thinkers, active in public life. We need to focus on nurturing. After all, “Fairy tales are the guide to good,, says our wise people.

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